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Research Article

**A CASE CONTROL STUDY ON THE RISK FACTORS
RELATED TO KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS**¹Dr Arooj Imtiaz, ²Dr Iqra Nisar, ²Dr Hina Tariq¹Allama Iqbal Medical College Lahore²Madina Teaching Hospital Faisalabad**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: One of the most frequent rheumatologic issue is knee OA (Osteoarthritis). We carried out this research work to examine the various risk factors associated with knee Osteoarthritis on the patients suffering from Stage-1 of disease according to COPCORD (Community Oriented Program for Control of Rheumatic Diseases).

Methodology: With the utilization of information from 2019-2020 COPCORD research work of Stage-1 that was performed in Lahore, Pakistan, the duration of this research work was from January 2019 to December 2020. There were seven hundred confirmed patients of knee Osteoarthritis according to criteria of ACR (American College of Rheumatology) and they were also seven hundred healthy controls with age and gender matched. The selection of the patients was carried out randomly from the general public.

Results: In this research work, we found a significant association between different studied factors and knee-Osteoarthritis and some of these risk factors are BMI (Body Mass Index) ($P < 0.0010$), lodging (living in plain vs. highland) ($P < 0.0010$), kind of the utilized toilet ($P < 0.0010$), past history of using the shoes with high heels (greater than three centimeters) ($P = 0.0050$), past history of injury to knee ($P = 0.040$), past history of fracture in lower limb ($P = 0.020$), total pregnancies number ($P < 0.0010$) and past history of swelling as well as pain (for 1 month) ($P = 0.040$).

Conclusions: Living in the areas of highland, utilization of regular toilet, past history of injury to knees and fracture to lower limb were the most important related risk factors with the prevalence of knee- Osteoarthritis.

KEYWORDS: Knee-Osteoarthritis, Risk, Pregnancy, Centimeters, Body Mas Index, Rheumatology, Fracture.

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INTRODUCTION:

One of the most widespread and rheumatic disease in humans which can lead to severe disabilities and chronic pains is the osteoarthritis (OA) [1]. Most common site of this disease is knee and knee-Osteoarthritis is the cause of disabilities in the patients of elder age [2]. There is occurrence of Osteoarthritis basically by the underlying reasons like fractures in past, injuries to bones, various infections, RA (Rheumatoid Arthritis), metabolic and congenital abnormalities and tumors [3, 4]. COPCORD has prescribed 3 stages including the determination of rate of occurrence of rheumatic complications and detection of associated risk factors; special training of physicians of primary health-care field, paramedical, improving the facilities of health care and researches for the environmental etiology for these rheumatic complications [5].

Stage-1 of COPCORD was performed during 2019-2020 and its findings including the incidence of knee issues in public were published in the next year [6]. Knee-Osteoarthritis is accountable for the high rate of morbidity especially in females and in the second half part of age when the QoL (Quality of Life) for the patients suffering from knee Osteoarthritis is an issue of worth importance [3, 7]. Regarding the significance and necessity of current research work, almost 1 out of 5 persons having age of more than fifteen years in area of Punjab had complaints of knees [6], while this rate was 1 out of 6 in region of Punjab according to one other national research work [5]. The aim of this research work was to find out the risk factors related with knee-Osteoarthritis in province of Punjab, Pakistan.

Table-I: Association Between Potential Risk Factors (Quantitative Variables) And Knee Osteoarthritis

Variables	Group	Mean	SD	P value
Body Mass Index	Case	28.8	4.3	<0.001
	Control	27.3	4.7	
Daily squatting or crouching (min)	Case	24.1	2.7	0.7
	Control	23.7	3.3	
Daily chair sitting (minutes)	Case	168.6	24.3	0.6
	Control	170.4	25.2	
Daily kneeling (minutes)	Case	15.5	2.1	0.8
	Control	14.8	1.7	
Using high-heeled shoes (>3cm) in the past	Case	4.6	1.7	0.004
	Control	4.2	1.3	
No. of pregnancies	Case	3.9	4.3	<0.001
	Control	3	3.7	
Duration of hypertension (years)	Case	11.3	8	<0.001
	Control	6.4	5.8	
Duration of other chronic diseases (years)	Case	17.6	12.6	<0.001
	Control	7.5	7.4	

METHODOLOGY:

This study was conducted in Lahore and the duration of this study was from January 2019 to December 2020. All the patients who were present with confirmed diagnosis of knee- Osteoarthritis with the utilization of ACR standard in COPCORD research work were the participants of this research work [6]. We selected the controls from healthy general public and all these persons were present without knee Osteoarthritis. We used the ACR criteria for the diagnosis of knee Osteoarthritis, pain in knee with minimum 3 out of total 6 criteria in the group of patients. There were seven hundred patients of knee Osteoarthritis who were selected randomly from 1099 patients of knee Osteoarthritis diagnosed at very first stage of the COPCORD research work. We selected one control for one case (controls were the healthy persons). We collected the data by taking the interview with the participants.

We used the SPSS V.23 for the statistical analysis of the collected information. On the first stage, we used the univariate analysis then for the factors that were statistically significant in that univariate analysis and some other qualitative and quantitative variables with $P < 0.10$ were evaluated with the logistic regression model, a multivariate analysis.

RESULTS:

Average age of the patients and their healthy controls were 51.80 ± 15.20 years and 52.50 ± 15.10 years respectively ($P = 0.40$). There were 64.0% subjects in both groups were females. Averages and standard deviations of interrogated quantitative variables in the participants of both groups and correlation with the knee Osteoarthritis are present in Table-1 in details.

Correlation between some other qualitative variables and knee- Osteoarthritis are available in Table-2. Results of the regression logistic model including P values, OR (Odds Ratio) and corresponding 95.0% CI (Confidence Intervals) for every factor are present in Table-3 with complete summary.

Table-II: Association Between Potential Risk Factors (Qualitative Variables) and Knee Osteoarthritis

Factors	Case n (%)	Control n (%)	P value	OR (95% CI)
Exercise			0.004	1.56 (1.15 - 2.12)
Yes	119 (59.5)	81 (40.5)		
No	581 (48.4)	619 (51.6)		
History of using high-heeled shoes (>3 cm)			0.008	1.42 (1.09 - 1.85)
Yes	163 (57.0)	123 (43.0)		
No	537 (48.2)	577 (51.8)		
Lodging			<0.001	5.24 (4.13 - 6.64)
living in highland area	554 (65.3)	294 (34.7)		
living in plain area	146 (26.4)	406 (73.6)		
Cigarette smoking			0.08	1.3 (0.97 - 1.72)
Yes	124 (55.3)	100 (44.7)		
No	576 (48.9)	600 (51.1)		
History of knee injury			<0.001	0.41 (0.2-0.6)
Yes	60 (69.8)	26 (30.2)		
No	640 (48.7)	674 (51.3)		
History of lower limb fracture			0.001	0.55 (0.30 - 0.80)
Yes	76 (63.3)	44 (36.7)		
No	624 (48.8)	656 (51.2)		
History of pain and swelling (lasting for one month)			0.007	1.34 (1.08 -1.65)
Yes	423 (53.1)	373 (46.9)		
No	277 (45.9)	327 (54.1)		
Menopause			0.032	1.36 (1.0-1.70)
Yes	268 (53.1)	237 (46.9)		
No	161 (45.5)	193 (54.5)		
Familial history of knee problems			<0.001	0.05 (1.1-1.4)
Yes	280 (56.3)	217 (43.7)		
No	360 (44.7)	446 (55.3)		
Diabetes			0.004	0.59 (0.41-0.81)
Yes	90 (61.2)	57 (38.8)		
No	601 (48.4)	641 (51.6)		
Hypertension			<0.001	0.60(0.4-0.7)
Yes	177 (59.4)	121 (40.6)		
No	506 (46.9)	574 (53.1)		
Other chronic diseases			0.09	0.80(0.6-1.0)
Yes	198 (53.8)	170 (46.2)		
No	495 (48.3)	529 (51.7)		
Type of toilet use			0.07	1.42 (0.97 - 2.08)
Regular	650 (50.7)	631(49.3)		
Toilet	50 (42.0)	69 (58.0)		

*OR: Odds Ratio, CI: Confidence Interval.

As presented in Table-3, the chance of the occurrence of knee- Osteoarthritis in the population living in the highland regions is about 5.67 times with a range from 4.40 to 7.31 times greater than the public living in plain regions. Some other factors which had statistically significant association with the knee Osteoarthritis were kind of the toilet utilized (OR: 2.280, CI: 1.470 - 3.550), having history of injury to knees in past (OR: 1.740, CI: 1.030 - 2.960) and patients having past history of fractures in their lower limbs (OR: 1.640, CI: 1.070 - 2.530).

Table-III: Potential Risk Factors Related to Knee Osteoarthritis (Logistic Regression Results)

Variable	OR (95% CI) *	P value
Age	1.01 (0.99 - 1.01)	0.1
Body Mass Index	1.09 (1.06 -1.12)	<0.001
Lodging (living in highland vs. plain)	5.67 (4.40 - 7.31)	<0.001
Cigarette smoking	1.22 (0.99 - 1.52)	0.06
Exercise	1.22 (0.86 - 1.73)	0.3
Toilet type use (regular vs. toilet)	2.28 (1.47 - 3.55)	<0.001
History of using high-heeled shoes (>3 cm)	1.53 (1.14 - 2.07)	0.005
History of knee injury	1.74 (1.03 - 2.96)	0.04
Familial history of knee problems	1.26 (0.98-1.62)	0.06
History of lower limb fracture	1.64 (1.07 - 2.53)	0.02
History of pain and swelling (lasting for 1 months)	1.31 (1.01 - 1.70)	0.04
N. of pregnancies	1.08 (1.05 -1.12)	<0.001
Diabetes	1.19 (0.80 - 1.80)	0.4
Hypertension	1.30 (0.95 - 1.80)	0.1
Other chronic disease	1.03 (0.80 - 1.36)	0.8

DISCUSSION:

In this current research work, we evaluated the possible risk factors associated to the knee-Osteoarthritis among the population of urban regions of Lahore city, located in the province of Punjab, Pakistan. This research work was conducted depending upon the previous COPCORD research that was conducted in the year of 2019-2020 [6]. In accordance with the findings of this research work, there were chances of high incidence of knee-Osteoarthritis with the increase of age. These results are much consistent with the findings of the research works conducted in past [7,8, 9]. In some other research works conducted in past, the most important risk factor for knee- Osteoarthritis as well as other musculoskeletal diseases was female gender and this particular difference in the gender distribution was because of the sensitivity of cartilage tissue to sex hormones, as the volume of knee cartilage is much higher in males as compared to females [10-12] but in this research work we could not evaluate the association between gender and knee- Osteoarthritis because of the individually matching controls and patients. Many national [13] as well as international research works [14-18] have already showed the impacts of high body mass index on the incidence of knee- Osteoarthritis.

Research work performed by El Ayoubi stated that residence regions and obesity are the important risk factors for the incidence of knee- Osteoarthritis [19]. This current research work also confirmed those results (P <0.0010). Even research work conducted

by Dahaghin also confirmed these findings [13]. Many other research works were also in favor that there is strong association of obesity with knee-Osteoarthritis [7, 20]. One other large study discovered that pooled odds ratio for the development of knee- Osteoarthritis was 2.63 times for obese patients as compared to normal healthy controls with normal weight. This research work discovered that people living in highland regions were more prone to suffer from knee- Osteoarthritis. Yoshimura also stated that there is high risk of knee-Osteoarthritis in the people who are living in mountainous areas as compared to the persons living in plain regions. Many research works conducted in past stated that long time downing, climbing, use of stairs and other associated life activities are the important risk factors for the development of knee-Osteoarthritis. The result of this current research work also showed that living in the high region that lead to daily climbing and coming down, is most important risk factor for the developing of the knee-Osteoarthritis (OR =5.670). There is need to study this factor in different regions to consolidate the findings of this research work. According to the findings of this research work, there was no association of knee- Osteoarthritis with smoking (P= 0.060). This result is full of controversies. The findings of the research work conducted by Haq are compatible with the results of this research work. But may research works have stated that positive impacts of smoking as a significant risk factor for the development of knee- Osteoarthritis. Usage of the regular toilet is also other important risk factor

for the development of knee- Osteoarthritis. Dahaghin in his research work conducted in Punjab also stated the similar results [13], but our finding is not similar with the results of Zeng [9]. Most of the population of our region is using the regular toilets because of cultural reasons and this point can be considered as preventable risk factor with intervention in a suitable way. Past history of the injury of knee and fractures of lower limbs are also important factors for the development of knee- Osteoarthritis which are already confirmed by one other research work. The fracture of lower limbs has an association with the development of knee- Osteoarthritis [7].

Although, there are many advantages of this current research work as adequate size of sample, methodological design, the control for the potential confounders with the utilization of the logistic regression and also the availability of the expert team, but the results of this current research work like many other case control studies may be influenced from recall bias in calculating the exposures and also incapability to evaluate the all acknowledged and unknown exposures for knee- Osteoarthritis like genetic and nutritional factors.

CONCLUSIONS:

On the basis of the findings of this current research work, it was concluded that living in the highland regions, utilization of the regular toilets, having history of injury to knees, fractures of lower limbs, high body mass index, use of shoes with high heels in past, having issues of swelling and pain lasting for more than one month in past few years and increase in the amounts of pregnancies are the most frequent risk factors for the prevalence of knee- Osteoarthritis.

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